

BITCOIN AND SOLAR ACTIVITY (2009-2025): $R=0.795$

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Abstract: A comparison of average Bitcoin prices in US dollars and average Wolf numbers for the solar cycle average for 2009–2025 allowed us to construct a model that explains 63.22% of the data variance. The author predicts a decline in the average annual Bitcoin price in 2026 and 2027.

Keywords: solar cycle, Wolf numbers, Bitcoin, economic cycle

Great scientists Frederick William Herschel, William Stanley Jevons and Alexander Leonidovich Chizhevsky developed a methodological approach to studying the connections between solar and economic activity in their works.

For example, in his article “Solar-Commercial Cycles” W. S. Jevons placed graphs of the CA cycles (Wolf number cycles) and the corn price cycles in Delhi one under the other for the period 1760-1810 [1, P.227].

A. L. Chizhevsky in his monograph “The Cosmic Pulse of Life: Earth in the Embrace of the Sun” in Chapter 4 “The Sun and Epidemics” in Fig. 33 constructed a diagram that shows **the average solar activity (SA) cycle** (Wolf number cycle) over a hundred years and the average number of cholera cases in Russia for the period 1823-1923 [2, p. 201].

In another monograph, "The Earth's Echo of Solar Storms," he placed graphs of grain yields in Russia and solar activity (SA) one under the other, which show a close direct connection between them [3, p. 106]. These graphs cover a long period of time.

This study compares the average annual Bitcoin price and the average Wolf numbers over the average (11-year) solar cycle from 2009 to 2025 on a single chart.

The annual mean Wolf numbers, the main indicator of solar activity, were taken from the well-known astrophysical website for the determination, conservation, and distribution of the international sunspot number [4]. They are presented in column 2 of Table 1.

The year numbers in column 3 of Table 1 are determined in accordance with the year numbering conventions used in solar astrophysics. Specifically, the first year in a solar cycle is considered to be the first year of its growth, i.e., the increase in the Wolf number. Subsequent years are numbered sequentially, and the last year in the cycle is considered to be the year of the Wolf number minimum.

Column 4 of Table 1 presents the average annual Bitcoin price calculated by Google Gemini artificial intelligence. The average annual Bitcoin price data is based on aggregated statistics from major analytics platforms and cryptocurrency exchanges. The primary data sources were Investing.com and Yahoo Finance, financial portals that maintain archives of exchange data. The average price for the year is calculated as the Average Daily Close—the arithmetic mean of the closing prices for all 365 (or 366) days of the corresponding year [5].

Table 1. Years, average annual Wolf numbers, ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles, and average annual prices of Bitcoin (2009-2025)

1.The years	2.Число Вольфа	3.The serial number of the year in the cycle of SA	4.Average annual price of Bitcoin
2009	4.8	1	0.0009
2010	24.9	2	0,3
2011	80.8	3	5
2012	84.5	4	8
2013	94	5	190
2014	113.3	6	530
2015	69.8	7	270
2016	39.8	8	570
2017	21.7	9	4000
2018	7	10	7500
2019	3.6	11	7300
2020	8.8	1	11100
2021	29.6	2	47400
2022	83.2	3	28200
2023	125.5	4	28800
2024	154.6	5	66000
2025	123.2	6	105000

The statistical data in Table 1 were then grouped by the ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles. The results of the data grouping in Table 1 are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Grouping of data from Table 1 by ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles

1. The serial number of the year in the cycle of SA	2. Number of years with this number for the period 2009-2025	Average arithmetic mean:	
		3. Wolf numbers, 2009-2025	4. Average annual price of Bitcoin
1	2	8.7	5550.00045
2	2	27.25	23700.03
3	2	82	14103.025
4	2	105	14404.23
5	2	124.3	34344.5
6	2	118.25	47363
7	1	69.8	272
8	1	39.8	567
9	1	21.7	4001
10	1	7	7558
11	1	3.6	7370
Итого:	17		
		Correlation coefficient:	
Rows 1-11, columns 3-4:	Average direct connection	0.66	

Based on the data in columns 3 and 4 of Table 2, a diagram was constructed (see Fig. 1). The coefficient of determination, equal to 0.63, means that the resulting model explains 63% of the variability (variation) in the data. The coefficient of determination of the polynomial model $R^2 = 0.6322$ corresponds to the correlation index $R = 0.795$.

Fig. 1. Average annual price of Bitcoin and average Wolf numbers (11 years of average solar cycle for 2009-2025), epoch superposition method

Although the calculation covers a 17-year observation period, the statistical significance of the model was calculated for 11 aggregated points representing the average values for each year of the 11-year solar activity cycle. The resulting p value of 0.018 confirms the statistical significance of the identified relationship at the 5% level ($p < 0.05$).

On the NASA website [6] there is a forecast of the development of the current 25th SA cycle (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Forecast of the development of the current 25th SA cycle

We see that a decrease in the Wolfe number is most likely in 2026 and 2027 (see the green curve). Therefore, as follows from the diagram in Figure 1, we should expect a further decline in the Bitcoin price in 2026 and 2027.

This work does not constitute investment advice.

Reference

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